

Electronic Spectra of some Heterocyclic Schiff Bases derived from 3-Amino-1,2,4-triazole

M. T. EL-HATY*, F. A. ADAM, A. E. MOHAMED and A. A. GABR

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Aswan, Egypt

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Electronic spectra of some heterocyclic Schiff bases derived from 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole in pure and mixed organic solvents of various polarities have been studied. Band assignments and spectra-structure correlations have been made. The possibility of the hydroxy derivatives to form hydrogen bonded molecular complexes with ethanol has been examined. The pK_a values of triazole ring and the different substituents attached to the aldehydic moiety have been determined.

THE study of spectral behaviour of aromatic Schiff bases has received a great deal of attention in recent years¹. The literature survey reveals that no similar studies have been carried on the Schiff base derived from 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole. The present work reports the study of medium effect on the spectra of some arylidenes-3-amino-1,2,4-triazole (1a-e) in pure and mixed organic solvents of different polarities and in buffer solutions of varying pH. The H-bonding solvated complexes formed in solution have been investigated. The pK_a values of the investigated compounds have been determined and discussed in the light of the Schiff bases molecular structures.

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1a; X = *p*-N(CH₃)₂ 1d; X = *p*-OH, *m*-OCH₃
1b; X = *o*-OH 1e; X = *p*-NO₂
1c; X = *p*-OH

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The organic solvents used (EtOH, CHCl₃, CCl₄, DMSO and dioxane) were of spectroscopic grade.

Heterocyclic Schiff bases were prepared according to the reported method². The purity of compounds was checked by microanalysis. Stock solutions (10⁻² mol dm⁻³) of compounds in each solvent were prepared by dissolving them in the appropriate solvent. The universal buffer series were prepared³. pH values were determined at 25° using a MV 87 digital pH meter (accuracy ± 0.05 units). The electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 240 spectrophotometer and the infrared spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 599 B spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Spectra in pure organic solvents: The electronic spectra (ethanol) of all compounds are recorded in Fig. 1. The λ_{max} and ϵ_{max} values obtained in various organic solvents are presented in Table 1

Fig. 1. Electronic absorption spectra of 5.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ of compounds 1a-e in ethanol at 25°.

The uv bands at 203–243 nm in the spectra of the compounds, are due to the excitation of the π -electrons of the aromatic system, since the position of these bands are least affected by changing the solvent polarity of the medium. Moreover, the position of these bands is quite sensitive to the substitution at this part of the molecule confirming their π - π^* nature.

TABLE 1 - ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPOUNDS 1a - e† IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT 25°

Compd. no.	DMSO		Ethanol		CHCl ₃		CCl ₄		Dioxane		Assignment
	λ _{max}	ε _{max}	λ _{max}	ε _{max}	λ _{max}	ε _{max}	λ _{max}	ε _{max}	λ _{max}	ε _{max}	
1a	-	-	204	13.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	π-π* ^a
	-	-	243	7.10	245	6.60	-	-	240	6.70	π-π* ^a
	345	20.50	348	22.60	342	21.20	333	20.30	333	20.00	π-π* ^b
	380sh	10.80	380sh	13.20	380	13.20	370	13.20	370	12.70	Intramol. CT trans.
1b	-	-	213	12.40	-	-	-	-	-	-	π-π* ^a
	232	8.20	230sh	8.80	240	6.10	254wb	6.00	255sh	5.30	π-π* ^a
	380wb	11.20	288wb	11.10	290wb	11.80	290wb	11.80	292wb	10.70	π-π* ^b
	300sh	10.20	300sh	9.20	300sh	10.70	300sh	10.70	308sh	9.10	Intramol. CT trans. ^c
	345	7.70	345	7.30	348	7.60	350	8.00	340	8.60	Intramol. CT trans. ^d
1c	-	-	203	9.30	-	-	-	-	-	-	π-π* ^a
	-	-	229	9.70	240	5.00	-	-	232	8.10	π-π* ^a
	298sh	13.40	298sh	13.40	298sh	13.90	299sh	12.80	298sh	14.50	π-π* ^b
	320	18.00	320	19.00	322	20.40	322	19.10	318	19.00	Intramol. CT trans. ^d
1d	-	-	205	12.40	-	-	-	-	-	-	π-π* ^a
	-	-	235	10.40	242	7.60	-	-	235	10.10	π-π* ^a
	289sh	8.00	287sh	8.40	285sh	8.40	285sh	8.40	285sh	8.40	π-π* ^b
	335	18.20	333	19.20	330	18.70	328	19.20	327	19.00	Intramol. CT trans. ^c
	-	-	400sh	1.32	-	-	-	-	-	-	Intramol. CT trans. ^d
1e	-	-	293	12.60	-	-	-	-	-	-	π-π* ^a
	320	13.00	308	13.50	313	14.70	312	14.30	314	14.60	Intramol. CT trans. ^d

*λ_{max} nm, ε_{max} × 10³ mol⁻¹ cm²; sh = shoulder, wb = weak band. ^aWithin aromatic system, ^bWithin central C=N group, ^cWithin enol form, ^dWithin keto form.

The uv band at 287–298 nm (except in case of 1a and 1e) is due to the transition between π orbitals largely localised on the central N=CH band⁴. The location of this band at longer wavelength (348 nm) in the spectrum of compound 1a suggests its influence by CT interaction occurring in the solute molecule. This behaviour is attributed to the high electron-releasing power of the -N(CH₃)₂ group. In case of compound 1e, this band is likely to be overlapped with the preceding strong π-π* band observed at 308 nm (ε_{max}=13 500 cm⁻¹ mol⁻¹ dm³).

The band observed at 300–400 nm is due to a transition within the whole molecule, essentially an intramolecular CT interaction. The good linear relationship obtained on plotting the absorbance of this band versus the molar concentration of each compound studied supports this explanation. Based on the electron-withdrawing character of the heterocyclic moiety⁵, the intramolecular CT interaction may be originated from the aryl moiety influenced by the substituent (X) to the hetero ring as acceptor centre as represented below,

Investigation of the solvent effect on the position of the observed bands (Fig. 2, Table 1)

Fig. 2. Electronic absorption spectra of 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ of compound 1a in organic solvents at 25°: (—) DMSO, (---) EtOH, (-.-) CHCl₃, (---) CCl₄ and (.....) dioxane.

indicates that λ_{max} of π-π* bands are slightly influenced by changing the solvent polarity, confirming the local excitation nature of these bands. On the other hand, the CT band exhibits a little red-shift in protic solvent (EtOH) relative to that in nonpolar solvent (dioxane). This behaviour can be ascribed to solute-EtOH interaction. This leaves a residual negative charge on the oxygen of OH group and positive charge on the nitrogen of N=CH group as presented by

Thus, the intramolecular CT is enhanced leading to a red-shift of this band. Also in the dipolar aprotic solvent (DMSO), the CT band exhibits low excitation energy relative to that in EtOH. This shift can be attributed to the low ionisation potential of DMSO (9.12 eV) relative to that in EtOH (10.49 eV)⁶. This will result in an easier CT from the lone-pair of electrons of the oxygen atom of DMSO than that from EtOH molecules.

The blue-shift observed in the position of the intramolecular CT band in case of compound 1e in ethanol relative to that in dioxane or in CCl₄ can be ascribed to the high electron-withdrawing character of the *p*-NO₂ group where it is likely to be considered as CT acceptor centre as presented below,

Accordingly, if the azomethine is protonated by proton transfer from ethanol, the CT interaction is expected to be difficult as reported by various workers⁷.

The splitting of the longer wavelength band into two bands in the spectra of hydroxy compounds (1b-d) can be interpreted on the principle of the possible existence of these compounds in solution as dynamic equilibrium mixtures in the tautomeric forms (OH...N) and (O...NH). Thus, one can ascribe the shorter wavelength visible band to intramolecular CT transition occurring within the enol form, while the band located at the longer wavelength to such transition within the keto form. On the other hand, the disappearance of the longer CT band in the spectra of *p*-hydroxy compounds (1c, d) in less polar or less H-bonding solvents is due to the expected predomination of the enol tautomer in these solvents, since the CT forces play an important role in the hydrogen bonding⁶. Moreover, the absence of this splitting in the spectra of 1a and 1e is in line with the suggested NH/OH form of hydroxy derivatives.

Molecular complex formation: In order to study the possibility of the formation of H-bonded solvated complexes between the solute molecules and proton-acceptor EtOH, electronic absorption spectral behaviour for *p*-hydroxy derivatives of triazole were investigated in mixed organic solvents. The spectral behaviour of compounds 1c (Fig. 3) and 1d in DMSO or CCl₄ containing successively increasing amounts of EtOH was studied. On

increasing the concentration of EtOH in the medium, a new shoulder is developed at longer wavelength which is attributed to an intermolecular CT within the hydrogen bonded solute-EtOH molecular complex formed in solution. The spectra recorded in the mixed solvents display a clear isosbestic point indicating the existence of an equilibrium between the H-bonded and the free solute molecules. This equilibrium can be represented as

Fig. 3. Electronic absorption spectra of 2.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} of compound 1c in EtOH-CCl₄ mixture at 25° with increasing amount of EtOH: (1) 17.17, (2) 15.45, (3) 10.30, (4) 6.87, (5) 6.01, (6) 5.15, (7) 3.43 and (8) 0.00M EtOH.

The effect of dielectric constant (*D*) of the medium is investigated by plotting the absorbance of the longer wavelength band as a function of (*D*) for all the systems investigated. The nonlinear relations obtained indicate that the spectral changes are governed by specific solute-solvent interaction, viz. hydrogen bonding which leads to the formation of the molecular complexes.

The formation constant (*K_f*) value of 1:1 molecular complex is determined from the variation of absorbance with increasing polar solvent concentration at given wavelength⁸ as follows,

$$K_f = \frac{[S \cdots \text{EtOH}]_n}{[S][\text{EtOH}]^n}$$

$$n \log [\text{EtOH}] = \log K_f + \log \frac{A - A_0}{A_x - A}$$

where *A*₀ is the absorbance in a low polarity solvent, *A_x* the absorbance in ethanol, *A* the absorbance in a mixed solvent, and *n* the number of associated ethanol molecules. The value of *n* can be evaluated from the slope of the plot, $\log(A - A_0)/(A_x - A)$ vs $\log [\text{EtOH}]$. The *n* values obtained are equal to one, supporting the 1:1 stoichiometry. The heat of molecular complex formation ΔG^* is determined from the relation, $\Delta G^* = -RT \ln K_f$. The values of *K_f* and ΔG^* for the solvated complexes are reported in Table 2. The results suggest that the molecular complexes are formed

through a weak intermolecular H-bond, which depends on the nature of low polarity solvent.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANT, HEAT OF FORMATION AND ABSORBANCE DATA OF COMPOUNDS IN MIXED ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Compd.	System	log K_f	K_f	$-\Delta G$ at 25° kcal mol ⁻¹	λ_{max} nm
1c	EtOH-DMSO	1.095	12.45	1.503	385
	EtOH-CCl ₄	0.91	8.13	1.249	385
1d	EtOH-DMSO	1.10	12.59	1.510	400
	EtOH-CCl ₄	1.02	10.47	1.400	400

Spectra in aqueous buffer solutions: A convincing evidence for the intramolecular CT nature of the longer wavelength band as well as the suggestion that the azomethine $\pi-\pi^*$ band is influenced by the CT interaction is achieved from a study of the spectral behaviour of the compounds in universal buffer solutions of the pH range 1.8–12.0 (Fig. 4). Generally, in solutions of low pH values

Fig. 4. Electronic absorption spectra of 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ of compound 1c in aqueous universal buffer solutions at 25° at different pH: (1) 11.00, (2) 10.00, (3) 9.00, (4) 8.75, (5) 8.50, (6) 8.35, (7) 8.25, (8) 8.05, (9) 7.50, (10) 7.00, (11) 6.50, (12) 6.30, (13) 6.00, (14) 5.75, (15) 5.50, (16) 5.00, (17) 3.60 and (18) 2.07.

(≤ 5.5) for all compounds (except 1a), the spectra exhibit mainly one band in the uv region, which is due to the excitation of the π -electron of the C=N perturbed by CT interaction. On increasing pH of the medium above 5.5, the intensity of this band decreases and its λ_{max} shifts to longer wavelengths (except in case of 1b). This can be ascribed to the deprotonation of the nitrogen atoms of the hetero ring as the pH of the medium is increased. This will increase the participation of the n -electrons of these nitrogen atoms in the CT within the hetero ring and hence an easier CT interaction is expected to occur. The blue-shift observed in case of compound 1b may be due to the protonation of the azomethine nitrogen atom in acid solutions, hence hindering the intramolecular hydrogen bond

existing in this compound between the *o*-OH group and the azomethine nitrogen atom. Accordingly, the molecules will lose some of its planarity and thus the CT interaction becomes difficult in such media.

In solutions of pH ≥ 7.3 , the second band attains more or less constant intensity, meanwhile a new band appears in all compounds except 1a, where its intensity increases by increasing pH of the medium. This band is assigned to an intramolecular CT transition.

The behaviour of the longer wavelength band can be attributed to an easier CT interaction as a result of high negative charge on the oxygen atom of the substituent (X) in the hydroxy compounds as well as the deprotonation of azomethine nitrogen atom in compound 1e as pH of the medium is increased.

Concerning the CT bands for the compound 1a, it is evident that the spectra recorded exhibit one band situated at the border of the visible region which is assigned to an intramolecular CT interaction. It is worthy to mention that no change is observed in the spectra of compound 1a at higher pHs (≥ 4.20). This indicates that the deprotonation processes of both the triazole ring and the $-N(CH_3)_2$ group take place within the lower pH range.

The spectra of the hydroxy compounds 1c–e display clear isobestic points at λ_{max} 297, 268 and 277 nm respectively, denoting the existence of an equilibrium between the protonated and neutral forms. Furthermore, these compounds are characterised by second isobestic points at higher pHs (λ_{max} 1c 334, 1d 340, 1e 327 nm) indicating the existence of a second equilibrium between the neutral and ionic forms of these compounds. Such equilibria can be represented as

Determination of acid dissociation constant: The spectrophotometric methods applied for the determination of the acid dissociation constant values (pK_a) are the half-wave height and the limiting absorbance methods⁹. The first method depends on the principle that $pK_a = \text{pH}$ at $A_{1/2}$ where

$$A_{1/2} = \frac{A_{max} - A_{min}}{2} + A_{min}$$

The second method depends on the relation,

$$\text{pH} = pK_a + \log \frac{(A - A_{min})}{(A_{max} - A)}$$

The value of pK_a can be evaluated from plot of $\log (A - A_{min}) / (A_{max} - A)$ vs pH, since $pK_a = \text{pH}$ value when

$$\log \frac{(A - A_{min})}{(A_{max} - A)} = 0$$

The limit of accuracy of the pK_a values was checked by making use of least-square method. The data obtained in Table 3, reveal the following

TABLE 3 - MEAN pK_a VALUES OF COMPOUNDS AT 25°

Compd. no.	pK_{a1}	pK_{a2}
1a	-	1.67 ± 0.02
1b	5.62×0.03	10.34 ± 0.04
1c	6.14×0.04	8.08 ± 0.07
1d	5.70×0.01	8.14 ± 0.04
1e	5.42×0.08	6.70 ± 0.25

facts. (i) The pK_a value for the compounds (except 1b) increases as the electron-donating character of the substituent (X) is increased. This is due to the easier CT towards the hetero ring in the same direction, which in turn increases the basicity of the hetero ring, i.e. high pK_1 . Thus, this behaviour can be considered as an evidence for the existence of some sort of co-planarity between the hetero ring and rest of the molecule. (ii) The very high pK_{a2} values observed for the *o*-hydroxy compounds support the suggestion that these compounds may exist in (OH...N/O...NH) equilibrium as suggested by Green and Sleet¹⁰. (iii) The pK_2 of compound 1b is higher than that of 1c, which is mainly due to the existence of

an intramolecular hydrogen bond in the former compound which in turn causes ionisation difficult of the OH group. (iv) The pK_1 value of the hetero ring is higher than that reported for the free triazole. This behaviour can be considered as evidence for the electron-withdrawing nature of the hetero ring.

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